

AWARENESS OF INVESTMENT ALTERNATIVES AMONG STUDENTS OF RAVENSHAW UNIVERSITY, CUTTACK

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Abstract

Investment decisions play an important role in shaping an individual's financial future, especially among young adults who are beginning to earn and manage money. This study examines the level of awareness and understanding of various investment alternatives among students of Ravenshaw University, Cuttack. The research focuses on commonly available investment options such as bank deposits, mutual funds, shares, insurance, real estate, gold, and government saving schemes. Data for the study were collected from students across different departments and academic levels using a structured questionnaire. The findings reveal that while most students are aware of traditional investment options like savings accounts and fixed deposits, their knowledge of market-linked and long-term investment avenues such as mutual funds, stocks, and retirement schemes is limited. The study also finds that factors such as financial literacy, family background, income level, and exposure to financial education significantly influence students' awareness and preferences. The paper highlights the need for improved financial education programs within the university to help students make informed investment decisions.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Investment Awareness, Investment Alternatives, University Students

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving economic environment and era of financial globalization, investment has become an essential part of personal financial planning. With the increasing complexity of financial markets and the availability of a wide range of investment options, it is important for individuals to have adequate financial knowledge and awareness. Investment decisions not only affect an individual's financial stability but also play a vital role in overall economic growth and capital formation. Therefore, understanding different investment

alternatives is especially important for young individuals who are just beginning their financial journey. Investment alternatives refer to the various avenues through which individuals can invest their savings to earn returns and achieve financial security. These include traditional options such as savings accounts, fixed deposits, post office schemes, and insurance, as well as modern alternatives like mutual funds, equities, bonds, exchange-traded funds, and systematic investment plans (SIPs). Each of these options differs in terms of risk, return, liquidity, and time period, making it essential for investors to choose according to their financial goals and risk tolerance. University students represent an important section of society as they are future professionals and investors. Developing awareness about investment alternatives at an early stage helps build good saving habits, encourages disciplined financial behaviour, and supports better decision-making. However, despite easy access to financial information through digital platforms, many students still lack practical knowledge and confidence in investing. Factors such as limited financial education, fear of risk, and misconceptions often prevent them from exploring different investment options.

Review of Literature

Mittal and Gupta (2025) study highlights that investors' awareness varies across different investment options and is strongly influenced by socio-economic and demographic factors. It also shows that investors consider factors like return stability, tax benefits, and convenience, emphasizing the importance of financial awareness for better investment decisions.

Harshini et al. (2025) shows that women generally have moderate awareness of investment options and prefer safer avenues like gold and mutual funds. Their investment decisions are influenced by factors such as risk, return, and social influences, highlighting the importance of financial literacy in improving their confidence and participation.

Salunkhe et al. (2020) found that awareness of alternative investment products among Mumbai investors is moderate, with limited full understanding. Age influences awareness and preferences, and traditional investments remain dominant. The study highlights the need for better financial education to improve informed investment decisions.

Lokhande (2015) shows that rural investors have limited awareness of modern investment options and prefer safe avenues like bank deposits and gold. Their decisions are largely influenced by socio-economic factors, and they focus more on safety and liquidity than high returns, highlighting the need for improved financial literacy.

Patil and Nandawar (2014) found that salaried individuals are generally aware of investment options but prefer safe avenues like bank deposits and real estate. Their decisions are mainly driven by safety, regular income, and tax benefits, showing a strong preference for low-risk investments.

Research Gap

Existing studies show that investment awareness varies across different groups, with most investors preferring low-risk options due to limited financial literacy. However, there is limited research focused on university students, especially at Ravenshaw University, Cuttack. Previous studies also overlook students' sources of information and challenges in understanding investment options. Therefore, this study aims to examine students' awareness, influencing factors, and difficulties in making investment decisions, aligning with its objectives.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the preferred investment option among students.
2. To compare the level of investment awareness among students of different streams.
3. To check whether commerce students possess higher investment awareness than arts and science students.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1:

- Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference in the level of awareness of investment alternatives among students belonging to different academic streams.
- Alternative hypothesis (H₁): There is significant difference in the level of awareness of investment alternatives among students belonging to different academic streams.

Hypothesis 2:

- Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference in the level of awareness of investment alternatives between students of Commerce streams and students of Arts and Science streams.
- Alternative hypothesis (H₁): There is significant difference in the level of awareness of investment alternatives between students of Commerce streams and students of Arts and Science streams.

Research Methodology

Data

- The present study is based solely on primary data. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire designed specifically for the purpose of the research.

Sample

- The sample size selected for the study consists of 120 respondents, who are students of Ravenshaw University. The respondents belong to different academic streams such as Commerce, Management, Arts, and Science, ensuring adequate representation from each stream.

Data analysis

- Descriptive statistical tools such as percentages and tabular presentation are used to identify investment alternatives known to students, and determine preferred investment options. For inferential analysis and hypothesis testing, Single Factor ANOVA and Two-Sample t-test assuming unequal variances are used.

Data Analysis

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Arts	36	108.4	3.011111	1.737587
Science	36	120.2	3.338889	1.63273
Commerce	48	161.4	3.3625	0.82367

The summary table shows investment awareness among Arts, Science, and Commerce students. Commerce students have the highest average awareness (3.36), followed by Science (3.34), while Arts students have the lowest (3.01). Arts and Science show higher variation, indicating mixed awareness levels, whereas Commerce students are more consistent. However, since the differences are small, ANOVA is needed to check statistical significance.

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	2.946389	2	1.473194	1.100145	0.33624	3.073763
Within Groups	156.6736	117	1.339091			

Total	159.62	119
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The ANOVA results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in investment awareness among Arts, Science, and Commerce students. The calculated F value (1.10) is lower than the critical F value (3.07), and the p-value (0.336) is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means the observed differences in average awareness scores across the three groups are not strong enough to be considered meaningful and may have occurred due to chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that students from different academic streams have similar levels of investment awareness.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Commerce</i>	<i>Arts & Science</i>
Mean	3.3625	3.175
Variance	0.82367	1.688662
Observations	48	72
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	118	
t Stat	0.930393	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.177034	
t Critical one-tail	1.65787	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.354067	
t Critical two-tail	1.980272	

The average awareness score of Commerce students (3.36) is slightly higher than that of Arts & Science students (3.18), but the difference is very small (about 0.19).

The variance shows that Arts & Science students have more variation in their awareness levels, while Commerce students are more consistent

The calculated t-value (0.93) is quite low, indicating that the difference between the two group means is not large compared to the variability in the data. More importantly, the p-value (0.354) is greater than the 0.05 significance level. This means the difference is not statistically significant and could have occurred by chance.

Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, and it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in investment awareness between Commerce and Arts & Science students.

Which investment option do you prefer the most ?

120 responses

The most preferred investment option among students is a savings account (39.2%), indicating a strong preference for safe and secure investments. This is followed by stock market/equity shares (13.3%), mutual funds (12.5%), and SIP and fixed deposits (10.8% each). Other options like digital gold, physical gold, and cryptocurrency have comparatively lower preference.

What motivates your preference for a particular investment option ?

120 responses

The majority of students are motivated by low risk (59.2%), followed by high returns (41.7%) and long-term safety (39.2%). Factors like ease of understanding and liquidity also play a moderate role, while recommendations and popularity have minimal influence.

Finding and Conclusion

The study reveals that most students are aware of basic and traditional investment options like savings accounts and fixed deposits, but their knowledge of modern investment avenues such as mutual funds, stocks, and SIPs is comparatively limited.

Among the different streams, Commerce students show slightly higher investment awareness, followed closely by Science students, while Arts students have the lowest awareness. However, statistical tests (ANOVA and t-test) confirm that these differences are not significant.

The most preferred investment option among students is the savings account, indicating a strong inclination towards safety. Other options like stocks, mutual funds, and SIPs are less preferred.

Students' investment decisions are mainly influenced by low risk, followed by high returns and long-term safety. Factors such as recommendations and popularity have very little impact.

The study concludes that although students have a basic understanding of investment options, their overall awareness is moderate and largely limited to low-risk alternatives. There is no significant difference in awareness across academic streams, indicating that financial knowledge is generally similar among students.

Students prefer safe and secure investment options due to risk aversion and limited financial literacy. Therefore, there is a strong need for financial education programs and practical exposure to modern investment tools.

Improving financial literacy will help students make better and more informed investment decisions in the future.

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